

CHILDREN AND BULLYING/HARASSMENT IN GRECO-ROMAN ANTIQUITY*

Abstract: Fully recognizing all the possible limitations and even objections to a historical inquiry into bullying and harassment in Antiquity, this article tackles the subject by strictly limiting the situations to be studied. It only takes into account those instances in which children or adolescents are both the agents and the victims of bullying and harassing behavior. It only looks at the interaction between children of free status. First, I study children in a stage of life in which they were largely subjected to the authority of parents and other educators. After this, the focus is on young girls, whose coming of age put them in a peculiar situation regarding harassment. Finally, student life is given due attention. In conclusion, I point out how a careful consideration of these fragments not only informs us about aspects of everyday life of young people in antiquity, but also about ancient concepts of personhood.

Keywords: bullying, childhood, girls, sexual harassment, youth

1. Introduction: Experience, Agency and the History of Ancient Childhood

Recently, experience and agency have been proposed as new paradigms for the social history of childhood and youth in antiquity. Fully acknowledging the difficulties in hearing the “tiny voices from the past,” scholars have approached well known source material with a fresh look and asked new research questions. They recognized that experiences as we encounter them in ancient texts are never simply reported but always processed and narrated. However, the mere fact that certain experiences are narrated is important by itself. Also, the focus on agency opens the possibility of a depiction of the potential of human networks (gender, age, social group, stage of life course, cultural area, time) and the way young people made a difference (both individually and collectively) in conditions that obviously also limited them. In all, the attention to experience and agency has resulted in a volume on ancient childhood with particular attention to the settings, activities, religions and negative aspects of this phase of life.¹

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In the wake of such new studies, this article sets out to examine a much under-explored aspect of ancient childhood: the extent to which children and young people bullied or harassed each other. Starting from an exhaustive survey of the terminology in the literary sources, I develop both a socio-cultural history of ancient bullying—which also implies a comparison with modern or other historical concept of bullying—and a literary analysis, which will demonstrate how bullying stories can be used to illustrate ancient notions and concepts of character and personhood.

For this, I study three situational contexts, which follow a life course approach. First, I look at children in a stage of life in which they were largely subjected to the authority of parents and other educators. After this, the focus will be on young girls, whose coming of age put them in a peculiar situation regarding harassment. Finally, student life will be given due attention, as we see young males abroad at “universities,” living in a situation of relative independence. Throughout this study, I regard antiquity as a period of a *longue durée*, from ancient Greece up to the late ancient world, circa 800 CE. Christian sources will indeed play an important part in this paper.² Before embarking upon these three contexts, it is crucial to look at ancient and modern concepts of bullying and harassment in order to ask whether the ancients had words for it.

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¹ Laes and Vuolanto (2017). See in particular the methodological chapters by Laes and Vuolanto (2017); Vuolanto (2017); Aasgaard (2017). Agency and experience seem to be particularly studied in a Scandinavian context: “Tiny Voices from the Past. New Perspectives on Childhood in Early Europe” (2013–17) was a project from the University of Oslo (Norway), while the University of Tampere (Finland) now runs the “Centre of Excellence in the History of Experiences.”

² Such *longue durée* is the explicit option of both Laes, Vuolanto (2017) and Aasgaard, Horn and Cojocararu (2018). The latter volume is one of the only on childhood in the past which has a “bullying” entry in the indices.

2. Words and Terminology: Ancient and Modern

In the wake of psychology and sociology, both bullying and harassment are now carefully defined and categorized concepts, used in the contexts of schools and education, professional relations and human interaction at large. For bullying, the often repeated and habitual use of force, threat, or coercion to abuse, intimidate, or aggressively dominate others is considered essential. Another essential prerequisite is the perception, by the bully or by others, of an imbalance of social or physical power, which distinguishes bullying from conflict. Next to the element of imbalance and domination, harassment connotes a sexual component.³

For at least two reasons, dealing with the subject from a socio-cultural point of view is highly problematic. First, if one is prepared to copy uncritically the definition as proposed by modern sociology and psychology, bullying and harassment become an empty receptacle in which one could store almost any relationship in ancient society: master and slave, husband and wife, parent and child, educator and pupil, soldier and civilian, *nobilior* and *humilior*—the list is by no means exhaustive. At best, such inquiry would lead to statements about ancient social relations being profoundly permeated by power relations enforced by physical means.⁴ Such conclusions have been drawn long before, and there is no need to introduce the terms “bullying” and “harassment” to reconfirm them.⁵ Second, the terms themselves are problematic from a historical point of view. The noun “bully,” meaning “sweetheart,” of Dutch and Middle High German origin, was first used in the 1530s and could be applied to either sex. Throughout the 17th

³ For definitions and categories of forms of bullying, see also Rigby (2002) 27–51. The World Health Organization recognizes the problematic of bullying and harassment. See <http://www.who.int/bulletin/volumes/88/6/10-077123/en/> (accessed on April 18, 2018) on bullying; <http://www.un.org/womenwatch/osagi/pdf/whatish.pdf> (accessed on April 18, 2018) on sexual harassment. The excellent Wikipedia entry on Bullying offers a rich conspectus of definitions, categories, and theories on the matter, for which the work by Dan Olweus in schools in Sweden and Norway (note again the Scandinavian context) from the 1970s on has been quintessential. The international Bullying Prevention Program, mostly for schools, draws on theories by Dan Olweus. See <https://olweus.sites.clemson.edu/index.html> (accessed on April 18, 2018).

⁴ Peachin (2011) is a classic in the field.

⁵ In an attempt to historicize and ‘prove’ the antiquity of bullying, Rigby (2002) 15–18 lists a series of quotations from the Psalms in which the author expresses his anger, his feeling oppressed by powerful oppressors and his longing for revenge. There is no discussion on terminology used (Hebrew, Greek or Latin), and at best Rigby is able to point to the fact that in the end human nature does not change a lot (2002) 22–6. He also points to bullying behavior with several animal species, as witnessed by ethologists (2002) 19–22.

century the meaning deteriorated from “fine fellow” to “harasser of the weak.”⁶ Though ancient Greek and Latin have a rich vocabulary to denote “harassing,” “ridiculing” and more broadly “showing superiority towards another person,”⁷ it makes little sense to search for good equivalents for “bullying” or “sexual harassment,” especially when one takes into consideration that even Italian and Modern Greek commonly use a transliteration of the English word (Italian *bullismo* and Greek το bullying), though native terms such as the Greek ο εκφοβισμός for bullying and the Italian *molestia* and Greek παρενόχληση for harassment also exist.

Fully recognizing all the possible limitations and even objections to a historical inquiry into bullying and harassment in Antiquity, I want to tackle the subject by strictly limiting the situations to be studied. I only take into account those instances in which children or adolescents are both the agents and the victims of the bullying and harassing behavior. As age limits, I take roughly the age of 25 for boys (the age at which full economic independence was achieved in Roman law) and twenty for girls (although legal majority and marriageable age were set at twelve, marriage could take place from the early to late teens—the wedding surely was an important factor for social majority).⁸ I will only look at the interaction between children of free status, since the institution of slavery by its very nature already affected the extent to which children might have bullied or harassed each other. Teachers, tutors or other educating adults will only be part of the story as far as their positions of authority encouraged children or young people to bully or harass their peers.⁹

⁶ Rigby (2002) 24–6, drawing on the *OED* s.v. The “lovely bully” appears with Shakespeare, *Henry IV*, Act IV, Sc. 1, 44–48. Rigby makes the point that “Many of us are still prone (at least in some moods) to admire the practitioner of force for personal ends” (25). In a way, the “positive” meaning of the word seems to have been somehow preserved.

⁷ γελᾶν, ἐν γέλῳτι ποιεῖσθαι/τιθέναι, ἐπιγελᾶν, ἐρεθίζειν, καταγελᾶν, καταπονεῖν, καταφρονεῖν, παίζειν, παρενοχλεῖν, ὑβρίζειν; *blasphemare, circumvenire, contemnere, decipere, despiciere, destituere, fallere, increpare, inequitare, insultare, irridere, ludere; ludibrio habere, mentiri; ridere.*

⁸ Laes and Vuolanto (2017) 5–6 following the options by Laes (2011) (childhood up to fifteen years of age); Laes and Strubbe (2014); Caldwell (2015) (girls and young married women).

⁹ As such, I will not deal with violence by or against educators. For the former, see Saller (1991); de Bruyn (1999); Laes (2005); Bloomer (2015). Bloomer (2017) 166–76 offers valuable observations on fantasies of escape and revenge, as well as acts of resistance. The theme of violence against educators is still much understudied, though there are significant anecdotes about e.g. Alcibiades fetching a teacher a blow with his fist (Plu. *Alc.* 7.1) or Heracles beating and killing his music teacher Linus. See Booth (1973); Stark (2013) 138–47 and 187–96; Laes (2019).

3. Children Bullying and Harassing Each Other

3.1 Bullying and Role Playing

Already in the 5th century BCE, Herodotus offers an eminent example of unpleasant consequences of role playing imposed by one child on another. The anecdote is about the so-called Game of the King, by which one young person assigned (unpleasant) tasks to a peer. The game was well known in the Roman period too.¹⁰ The main subject with Herodotus is the later king of Persia Cyrus the Great, who as a boy was thought to be the son of a cowherd of Median king Astyages (r. 585–50 BCE). In reality, he was the grandson of the Median king himself, who had married his daughter Mandane to his Persian vassal Cambyses I. Astyages had ordered his general Harpagus to dispose of his baby grandson, since he had been told in a dream that his grandson would eventually bring down the Median kingdom. General Harpagus could not bring himself to kill the child and had handed him over to a couple of herdsmen. Cyrus' true royal nature was discovered after the following incident (Hdt. 1.114-15):

Now when the boy was ten years old, it was revealed in some such wise as this who he was. He was playing in the village where these herdsmen's quarters were: there he was playing in the road with others of his age. The boys in their play chose for their king that one who passed for the son of the cowherd. Then he set them severally to their tasks, some to the building of houses, some to be his bodyguard, one (as I suppose) to be the King's Eye; to another he gave the right of bringing him messages; to each he gave his proper work. Now one of these boys who played with him was son to Artembares, a notable Median; as he did not obey the command Cyrus gave him, Cyrus bade the other boys seize him, and when they did so he dealt very roughly with the boy and scourged him. As soon as he was loosed, very angry at the wrong done him, he went down to his father in the city and complained of what he had met with at the hands of the son of Astyages' cowherd,—not calling him Cyrus, for that name had not yet been given. Artembares went with his anger fresh upon him to Astyages, bringing his son and telling of the cruel usage he had had: "O King," said he, "see the outrage done to us by the son of your slave, the son of a cowherd!" and with that he showed his son's shoulders. When Astyages heard and saw, he was ready to avenge the boy in

¹⁰ On this game, see Poll. 9.110: "*basilinda* means that a king is chosen by lot. He then orders what needs to be done. The one who is allotted to be the servant has to work out under the king's command whatever has been ordered" (βασιλινδα μὲν οὖν ἐστὶν ὅταν διακληρωθέντες ὁ μὲν βασιλεὺς τις ὧν τάττει τὸ πρακτέον, ὁ δ' ὑπηρέτης εἶναι λαχὼν πᾶν τὸ ταχθὲν ὑπεκτονῆ; my translation).

justice to Artembares' rank: so he sent for the cowherd and his son. When they were both present, Astyages said, fixing his eyes on Cyrus, "Is it you, then, the son of such a father, who have dared to deal so despitefully with the son of the greatest of my courtiers?" "Yes, master," answered Cyrus, "what I did to him I did with justice. The boys of the village, of whom he was one, chose me in their play to be their king: for they thought me the fittest to rule. The other boys then did as I bid them: but this one was disobedient and cared nothing for me, till he got his deserts. So now if I deserve punishment for this, here am I to take it." (trans. A. D. Godley)

This story needs to be understood in its literary and narrative context. In fact, it refers to Deioces (r. 727–675 BCE), whom the Medes had chosen as their first king, and for whom they provided houses and bodyguards (though he himself preferred one stronghold; 1.97–8)—exactly the kind of tasks the young Cyrus assigned to his peers. By wanting to have the same provisions that were at the disposal of the first Median king, the presumed son of a cowherd showed that more was in him. After his true royal nature was revealed, he succeeded his father as Persian king in 559 BCE, and in 550 BCE took over the Median kingdom of his grandfather. Be this as it may be, the anecdote also offers a unique glimpse of both the possible tensions which might arise when a presumed social inferior was allotted the role of king, and the potential rough character of the play (the stripes on the boy's shoulder as traces of the harsh whipping).

The Herodotean story on the foretelling character of role playing and the Game of the King possibly resonates in an anecdote with Tacitus. The scene brings us to the celebration of the Saturnalia festivities at the imperial palace in December 54. At that moment, the newly appointed emperor Nero was seventeen years of age, while the young prince Britannicus was thirteen years old and still had to be donned the *toga virilis*, the symbol of his coming of age and adulthood. Tacitus understands the incident as the culmination of former frictions between Nero and Britannicus. Since the latter continuously addressed his half-brother as Ahenobarbus—pointing to the name of his biological father—Nero tried to persuade Emperor Claudius that Britannicus was in fact a supposititious child. According to Suetonius, Nero was jealous of Britannicus' beautiful voice and success in singing (Tac. *Ann.* 13.15):¹¹

¹¹ Suet. *Ner.* 7 and 33.

Perturbed by her attitude, and faced with the approach of the day on which Britannicus completed his fourteenth year, Nero began to revolve, now his mother's proclivity to violence, now the character of his rival,—lately revealed by a test which, trivial as it was, had gained him wide sympathy. During the festivities of the Saturnalia, while his peers in age were varying their diversions (*inter alia aequalium ludicra*) by throwing dice for a king, the lot had fallen upon Nero. On the others he imposed various orders, not likely to put them to the blush: but, when he commanded Britannicus to rise, advance into the centre, and strike up a song—this, in the hope of turning into derision a boy (*pueri*) who knew little of sober, much less of drunken, society—his victim firmly began a poem hinting at his expulsion from his father's house and throne. His bearing awoke a pity the more obvious that night and revelry had banished dissimulation. (trans. J. Jackson)

Other sources confirm that the one who had been designated king by the throwing of the dice could indeed impose orders on his fellow players.¹² It was very much dependent on the character of the one in command and the one receiving orders whether such task turned out to be a pleasant one or rather the opposite. In the case of the shy, young prince, who had just experienced the unexpected and rather suspicious death of his father and his being denied the throne, the order of singing in public might have been embarrassing to say the least. Yet, while a modern audience would primarily think of the psychological burden imposed on young Britannicus (in fact, the incident could be the culmination of repeated intimidation), Tacitus' reading is profoundly different. He is eager to stress the ominous character of the event. Britannicus indeed showed moral strength, and the conflict between the two opponents was eminently visible in the events that ensued from this performance. In fact, we are also invited to read Britannicus' refusal to refer to Nero by his adoptive name as a form of resistance, even an insult which the emperor repaid by the forceful command to sing in public.

In the *Life of Cato Minor*, a text almost contemporary to Tacitus' account, Plutarch offers a most remarkable account of a game of playing judge, which turned into sexual molestation; the reference to “a goodlooking boy being shut up” — τῶν ἐαλωκότων παίδων εὐπρεπῆς τὴν ὄψιν—has an obvious sexual innuendo in it (Plu. *Cat. Mi.* 2.5–6):

¹² Epict. *Diss.* 1.25.8: Ἐν Σατορναλίοις λέλογχε βασιλεύς· ἔδοξε γὰρ παιῖται ταύτην τὴν παιδιάν. προστάσσει “σὺ πίε, σὺ κέρασον, σὺ ἄσον, σὺ ἄπελθε, σὺ ἐλθέ.”

At another time a relation of his who was celebrating a birthday, invited Cato and other boys to supper, and the company were diverting themselves at play in a separate part of the house, older and younger together, their play being actions at law, accusations, and the conducting of the condemned persons to prison. Accordingly, one of those thus condemned, a boy of comely looks, was led off by an older boy and shut into a chamber, where he called upon Cato for help. Then Cato, when he understood what was going on, quickly came to the door, pushed aside the boys who stood before it and tried to stop him, led forth the prisoner, and went off home with him in a passion, followed by other boys also. (trans. B. Perrin)

Here as well, attention to the narrative context is much needed. The story is situated during Cato's childhood years and foresees the sense of justice with which he was imbued from early youth. It comes right after a passage that illustrates young Cato's steadfastness, placed in the year 91 BCE, when Cato was only four years of age. Pompaedius Silo, a friend of Livius Drusus, lodged with him for several days. Also present at the house were young Cato together with his brother Caepio, his sister Porcia and his half-sister Servilia—all of whom were raised in the house of their maternal uncle Livius Drusus. During this time, Pompaedius became familiar with the children (τοῖς παιδίοις). When he jokingly asked whether they would help him in his struggle for citizenship, Caepio consented with a smile, but Cato remained silent. Since he persisted in his silence, giving the impression of not consenting, Pompaedius lifted the young boy up through a window, as if he would cast him out, and ordered him to consent, or he would throw him down. Despite Pompaedius' menaces, his harsh voice and his frequent shaking the boy, Cato endured the treatment and showed no fear. In the end, Pompaedius put him down, saying quietly to his friends that if this boy were a man, they could not get a single vote for citizenship among the people.¹³

Again, attention to the narrative context does not exclude the study of social reality behind the scene. What we see is an unspecified relative of Cato having a birthday party, with children of various families and ages gathering together (συγγενοῦς τινος ἐν γενεθλίοις καλέσαντος ἐπὶ δείπνον ἄλλους τε παῖδας καὶ τοὺς περὶ Κάτωνα). It is precisely the age difference which caused the abuse of power and the consequent harassment by one of the older boys. Presumably, the host was not a child himself: the children were put in a separate part of the house, where they had their own party, playing actions at law and accusations.

¹³ Plu. *Cat. Mi.* 2.1–5.

Also, other passages refer to the predictive element in role playing games. Ancient writers assigned a predictive role to such play,¹⁴ as they also compared role playing of children with adults who take their “games” far too serious.¹⁵ As such, Emperor Nero had his stepson Rufrius Crispinus, a son of Poppaea’s first marriage, killed while he was still a minor (*impuberem*) because he indulged in playing the emperor.¹⁶ In the *Historia Augusta*, we learn that the only game Septimius Severus at a very young age enjoyed to engage in with other children was playing judge. Would the judgments he gave imply some cruel punishment towards other children who played with him, while he was standing with the rods and axes before him, and surrounded by the throng of children? The ancient biographer does not elaborate on this detail, though he obviously regarded playing judge as predictive for the role of Septimius Severus in adult life.¹⁷

Role playing with a predictive value continued in Byzantine hagiography. In the *Life of Athanasios of Athos*, we read that the other children did not chose young Athanasios as an emperor or a general in their role play. Neither did they make him a bridegroom (as children usually do). They rather appointed him as a leader and legislator of monastic life, and the children obeyed him in this.¹⁸ Bullying behavior or sexual harassment do not seem to appear in the hagiographical tradition on role playing.

¹⁴ As Plu. *Cat Mi* 3.1 on the young Cato’s leading role in the equestrian Trojan game. Néraudau (1984) 234–6 on children’s participation in the Trojan game, often predictive of their later status.

¹⁵ Sen. *Const.* 12.2: “For while children are greedy for knuckle-bones, nuts and coppers, these are greedy for gold and silver and cities; while children play among themselves at being magistrates, and in make-believe have their bordered toga, lictors’ rods and tribunal, these play in earnest at the same things in the Campus Martius and the forum and the senate; while children rear their toy houses on the sea-shore with heaps of sand, these, as though engaged in a mighty enterprise, are busied in piling up stones and walls and roofs, and convert what was intended as a protection to the body into a menace” (trans. J. W. Basore). See also Hor. *Epist.* 1.18.60–4 on young Maximus Lollius who together with his brother in a sham fight on their father’s estate have represented the battle of Actium.

¹⁶ Suet. *Ner.* 35.5.

¹⁷ SHA *Sev.* 1.4: “While still a child, even before he had been drilled in the Latin and Greek literatures (with which he was very well acquainted), he would engage in no game with the other children except playing judge, and on such occasions he would have the rods and axes borne before him, and, surrounded by the throng of children, he would take his seat and thus give judgments” (*In prima pueritia, priusquam Latinis Graecisque litteris imbueretur, quibus eruditissimus fuit, nullum alium inter pueros ludum nisi ad iudices exercuit, cum ipse praelatis fascibus ac securibus ordine puerorum circumstante sederet ac iudicaret*; transl. D. Magie).

¹⁸ *Life of Athanasios of Athos* 2–3. See the translation by Talbot in Greenfield and Talbot (2016) 128–367, esp. 133–5.

3.2 *Bullying and Play*

Ancient authors acknowledge that children's playing was sometimes proverbially rough, impetuous or violent.¹⁹ "Children excel in the art of teasing" was the succinct way in which a historian of ancient childhood put it.²⁰ Such teasing should not be understood in an all too pleasant way.²¹ According to Plutarch, the sage Bion remarked that boys (τὰ παιδάρια) throw stones at frogs for fun, but the frogs do not die for fun.²² Another fragment mentions a young man (τοῦ νεανίσκου) throwing a stone at a dog.²³ John Chrysostom confirms what we read in the non-Christian authors: if a small child was seen picking up a stone, the Church Father states that everyone will call out, "Don't throw it!"²⁴ While rough and violent play has a potential for stories about habitual or repeated targeting of especially vulnerable children, the ancient sources do not mention a single instance of this. The authors do not seem particularly interested in how children behaved to each other.

This also counts for other cases. We are sometimes informed of particularities of games, in which the potential of malicious teasing and/or bullying can easily be imagined. In the *chytrinda*-game ("The Game of the Cooking Pot"), one player was put in the center of a circle and called "the cooking pot." The other players would tease, pull his hairs and beat him, while "the cooking pot" himself tries to

¹⁹ Plu. *De virt. mor.* 7.447a: "Just as the sudden assaults of children have an impetuosity and violence that is precarious and inconstant because of children's weakness" (ὡςπερ αἱ τῶν παιδῶν ἐπιδρομαὶ τὸ ῥαγδαῖον καὶ τὸ σφοδρὸν ἐπισφαλὲς ὑπ' ἀσθενείας καὶ ἀβέβαιον ἔχουσι; trans. W. C. Helmbold). Other statements explicitly point to playing in streets. See Plu. *De coh. ira* 10.458d on children who run races, and, through lack of self-control, fall down ridiculously before they reach the goal toward which they are hastening. In Plu. *Alc.* 2.2–4, we read the story about Alcibiades who as a small boy was playing knucklebones in a narrow street. A driver with a heavy-laden waggon disturbed the children's play, but Alcibiades threw himself flat on his face in front of the team, stretched himself out at full length, and bade the driver go on if he pleased.

²⁰ Eyben (1996) 102.

²¹ In fact, ancient authors acknowledged that children could be potentially cruel and wicked, witness the Hellenistic sculpture of a child strangling a goose. See Bradley (1998) and Kleijwegt (2004) c. 873.

²² Plu. *De soll. an.* 7.965b.

²³ The anecdote is worth quoting in full. See Plu. *Sept. Sap. Conv.* 2.147c "... of the young man who threw a stone at his dog, but hit his stepmother, whereupon he exclaimed, 'Not so bad after all!'" (trans. W. C. Helmbold). The story is repeated in Plu. *De tranq. an.* 39.467c, but here the perpetrator is not named with an age-specific term.

²⁴ Ioh. Chrys. *Hom. epist. ad Col.* 4.4 (PG62.330). See Leyerle (1997) 256.

grasp one of his attackers, who would then be put in the middle of the circle.²⁵ The game called *chalke muia* was an ancient version of blind man's bluff. One boy was put on a blindfold and walked around while shouting "I chase the fly." His fellows replied, "You chase the fly, but you cannot catch it," while beating him with strips of papyrus. This went on until he caught one of his attackers, who would then presumably take his place.²⁶ The female version of the *chalke muia* was called *chelichelone* ("Game of the Turtle"), and we are told that this was played by young and unmarried girls.²⁷ Despite the potential for bullying, the ancient authors do not elaborate on the (psychological) consequences for the victims of such playing.²⁸

3.3 Bullying in School Context

Bullying in ancient school context raises the question whether the agonistic and litigious nature of ancient Greek and Roman education led to cases of children systematically bullying and harassing each other. The ancient writers were aware that rivalry was very much part and parcel of the ancient education system,²⁹ but an anecdote concerning the precocity of young Cicero mentions that his peers actually admired him. They did not bully him or vice versa.³⁰ In fact, there is little to no evidence about repeated bullying of fellow pupils in ancient schools, despite of the fact that ancient authors were aware that interaction between young agemates was often rough.³¹ Only in the biographies of "villainous" Roman emperors, one finds occasional references to bullying. The emperor Heliogabalus

²⁵ Poll. 9.113–14: ἡ δὲ χυτρίνδα, ὁ μὲν ἐν μέσῳ κάθηται καὶ καλεῖται χύτρα, οἱ δὲ τῶν ἄλλων ἢ κνίζουσιν ἢ καὶ παίουσιν αὐτὸν περιθέοντες. ὁ δ' ὑπ' αὐτοῦ περιστροφόμενος ληφθεὶς ἀντ' αὐτοῦ κάθηται.

²⁶ Poll. 9.123: ἡ δὲ χαλκὴ μῦια, ταινία τῶ ὀφθαλμῷ περισφίγγαντες ἐνὸς παιδός, ὁ μὲν περιστρέφεται κηρύττων. "χαλκὴν μῦϊαν θηράσω". Οἱ δὲ ἀποκρινόμενοι. "θηράσεις, ἀλλ' οὐ λήψει" σκυτέσι βυβλίνους αὐτὸν παίουσιν, ἕως τινὸς αὐτῶν λάβηται.

²⁷ Poll. 9.125: ἡ δὲ χελιχελώνη, παρθένων ἐστὶν ἡ παιδία, παρόμοιον τι ἔχουσα τῇ χύτρῃ.

²⁸ Costanza (2017) 85 considers the possibility of "bullismo" in the context of the scape goat mechanism, but carefully sticks to the more 'sober' observations by Pollux.

²⁹ Plu. *Arist.* 1–2 mentions how Themistocles and Aristides even as boys and fellow-pupils (παῖδας ὄντας αὐτοῦ καὶ συντρεφόμενους), from the outset, in every word and deed, were at variance with one another. For ambition towards fellows in the Spartan system, see e.g. Plu. *Lys.* 2.2–4 and *Ages.* 2.2.

³⁰ Plu. *Cic.* 2.2–3: Other pupils' fathers came to visit the school in order to see Cicero with their own eyes. The ruder ones among them were angry at their sons when they saw them walking with Cicero placed in their midst as a mark of honor.

³¹ Ioh. Chrys. *De inan. glor.* 29 (SC188.120); *Hom. epist. ad Col.* 4.3 (PG62.329). See Leyerle (1997) 256.

as a boy was nicknamed Varius by his school-fellows (*a condiscipulis*), because he seemed to be sprung from the seed of “various” men, as would be the case with “the son of a whore.”³² “The signs of a haughty and warlike spirit” (*animi iam tum militaris et superbi*) are stressed in the biography of the emperor Clodius Albinus, who as a schoolboy in Africa used to recite over and over again to the other children the following Vergilian verse: “Madly I seized my arms, though in arms there lay little reason” (*Arma amens capio, nec sat rationis in armis, Aen. 2.314*).³³ It is possible that he did more than just impress his peers by his repeated recitation of this particular verse.

In all, the relative silence in anecdotes about school life and the complete absence of references to school bullying among peers with ancient theorists of education as Cicero or Quintilian may be explained by the fact that an essential part of being a student was that former students mainly wrote of the happier prospects and coming into power after the hardships of school life. The “real adult” world was reserved for the well-schooled free men who did not use physical violence against each other, but rather resorted to other verbal forms of competition as law or formal speech. In such a scheme, the bitter memory of unpleasant encounters with peers was rather irrelevant—and, one may add, the hardships suffered by teachers and other educators considered more relevant.³⁴

While the theme of school bullying is hardly emphasized in the Greco-Roman sources, it became part of the Byzantine hagiographical tradition.³⁵ Theodore of Edessa (9th century) was handed over to a teacher to learn to read and write at the age of five. Two years later, the boy was still unable to read the letters, for which he was rebuked by his classmates, the teacher and his parents.³⁶ The story fits into an hagiographical tradition of miraculous instruction, where divine intervention restores the ability to learn and acquire wisdom.³⁷ We may suspect similar motives

³² SHA *Heliogab. 2.2–3: et aiunt quidam Varii etiam nomen idcirco eodem inditum a condiscipulis quod vario semine, de meretrice utpote, conceptus videretur*. In D.C. 79.6.2 we read that Heliogabalus' mother Soaemias had a sexual relation with the boy's tutor Gannys. SHA *Heliogab. 9.2* mentions how Heliogabalus was often publicly mocked (*ludibrium publicum*).

³³ SHA *Clod. 5.1–2*.

³⁴ See the seminal conclusions in Bloomer (2017) 174.

³⁵ As such, bullying gets explicit attention in Cojocar (2016) 98 and 146–7 (Theodore of Edessa); 120 (Antony Kauleas).

³⁶ *Life of Theodore of Edessa 4* (p. 5), edited by Pomjalovskij (1892).

³⁷ Kalogeras (2006) 116–19 on Theodore of Edessa. Kalogeras points to the possibility of the young Theodore having a learning disability, perhaps augmented by the fact that he started school at a very young age. He rightfully adds that this is not something with which the Byzantine hagiographers concern themselves. However, he does not elaborate on the topic of bullying.

in the *Life of Antony Kauleas*, in which we read that the father decided not to enroll his five-year-old boy in school in order to avoid “the mockery of the other boys and other boyish sarcasm” (τοὺς τῶν παιδῶν ἐπιτωθασμοὺς καὶ τὴν ἄλλην μαιρακιώδη τερθρείαν).³⁸ In later Byzantine traditions,³⁹ Germanos Maroules (1252–1336) was said to be an assiduous student. For this, he was ridiculed and even physically bullied by his peers. As a true saint, however, he suffered this bullying in silence.⁴⁰

3.4 “Disability Hate Crimes”?

Though every term of the word group “disability hate crimes” is problematic as far as antiquity is concerned, it goes without saying that people in ancient society were at times mocked for their appearance which defied expectations.⁴¹

Occasionally, we find indications that such reactions were initiated by young people against peers. This is at least suggested in the case of the Spartan king Agesilaus II, whose deformity (τὴν δὲ τοῦ σκέλους πήρωσιν) was compensated by the beauty of his person in its youthful prime. He was in fact the first to jest and joke about himself.⁴² Mockery by peers is even more clear in the case of Demosthenes, who because of his bodily weakness and fragility did not pursue the studies he should have as a young man. Moreover, the offensive nickname of Batalus is said to have been given him to him by other boys in mockery of his physique (σκωπτόμενος ὑπὸ τῶν παιδῶν λαβεῖν).⁴³ With regards to emperor Claudius, a variety of evidence suggests disdain, mockery and subsequent exclusion from public life in childhood and youth. He is said to have been held in utter contempt by his mother Antonia the Younger and his grandmother Livia. Interesting for the present paper is the information that his sister Livilla, who was about three years older than Claudius, openly prayed that the Roman people

³⁸ *Life of Antony Kauleas* 3 (p. 414), edited by Leone (1989). Again, this fits in an hagiographical tradition of saints refusing to attend school so as to avoid the company of unruly schoolmates. See Kalogeras (2001). The tradition already starts with the *Life of Saint Antony*: When saints are going to school, the classmates are depicted primarily as unruly subjects whom the precocious holy children look down upon. See Kalogeras (2001) 6–7.

³⁹ Talbot (2018) 240–56.

⁴⁰ *Life of Germanos Maroules* 3–4 (p. 98–107), edited by Tsames (1985).

⁴¹ Laes (2018) 218 has over ten entries for “ridicule” in the general index. See also Laes (2008) 114–16 for mockery, with special attention to disabled children.

⁴² Plu. *Ages.* 2.3. Agesilaus deformity is studied from the standpoint of disability studies by Luther (2000) and Samama (2013) 239–41.

⁴³ Plu. *Dem.* 4.3–5. Plutarch mentions that Batalus might refer to effeminacy, or even to one of the parts of the body which it is not decent to name. On Demosthenes from the standpoint of disability studies, see Laes (2013) 173–4.

might be spared the possibility of having him as an emperor. He usually ate with his friends Sulpicius and Athenodorus, perhaps not the best folks to be with (as suggested in a letter by Augustus). Should we imagine the three of them forming an alliance of those who felt rejected in the palace?⁴⁴

In all, there are very few instances in which ancient sources explicitly testify of children or young people mocking each other because of deformity or disability. One Christian source seems to be more concerned with inner feelings caused by such mockery. Such is at least referred to in an every-day-life example from the apocryphal *Acts of Philippus*. Nicoclide's daughter Charitine, possibly a teenage unmarried girl, was scoffed at because of a stroke or a scar on her eye: her companions laughed at it, until she felt so ashamed she could not stand the insults anymore.⁴⁵

3.5 Group Pressure?

The same Christian emphasis on introspection appears when dominant members of a group put pressure on others to perform things they would not have done otherwise. Reflecting on a pear theft, which took place when he was sixteen-years old (he calls his companions *adulescentuli*), Augustine utters the following remarks (August. *Conf.* 2.9.17):

O my God, see the living memory of my soul in your presence! I would not have committed that theft on my own, a theft in which it was not the stolen items that pleased me but the very act of thieving. It definitely would not have pleased me to do it alone, nor would I have done it. What an extremely alien alliance it was—an unsearchable distraction of the mind! Out of a game and a lark came an eagerness to do harm, a taste for inflicting losses on others without myself gaining anything, or enjoying settling a score. Once someone says, "Come on, let's do it," it is shameful to be anything but shameless. (trans. C.J.B. Hammond)

This passage fundamentally needs to be understood in a theological way.⁴⁶ At the same time, Augustine in a remarkably vivid way describes the mechanism we now

⁴⁴ Suet. *Claud.* 3 (mockery by grandmother, mother and sister); 4 (Augustus' letter); 6 (laughing stock). See Laes (2013) 163–7.

⁴⁵ *Acta Philippi* 4.4–6.

⁴⁶ In a binary scheme, the pear tree as a tree of sin is placed against the fig tree as the tree of salvation. See e.g. Ferrari (1970) 233–42 for a theological study on this passage.

call group pressure. As such, Christian authors were the first to warn young people against the possibly detrimental effects of being part of an age group.⁴⁷

The same vivacity and psychological detail appears in the *Life of Theodore of Sykeon*, a 7th-century text. When Theodore was twelve-years old, the devil in the guise of his classmate Gerontios took Theodore and brought him to the precipice of a place called Tzidrama. He placed him on a high rock and dared him to jump off the cliff to prove his courage. When Theodore looked down, he was utterly afraid, but the devil/classmate assured him that there was no danger in the game. Theodore prudently proposed: “If you can make it, I can make it as well.” Gerontios jumped off the cliff and exhorted Theodore to do the same. “If you can,” he said, “come on and show me whether you are as brave in this as in all the others.” The child thought about it but was constrained by fear. At the last moment, however, Theodore showed good judgement. The poor child was eventually saved by the intervention of the martyr George, who held his hand and revealed to him that the schoolmate was not Gerontios but the devil. Obviously, the hagiographer did not view this whole incident as a dangerous game between two children. To him, it was about the fight between an infant prodigy and the devil. But of course, the readers might have understood it as a scene from real life, with one child repeatedly putting pressure on the other to behave as courageous as himself.⁴⁸

3.6 Did Educators React to Bullying?

One again has to wait for Christian authors for thoughts on how or whether to react against children bullying each other. For this, John Chrysostom is once more revealing. He acknowledges that when older children get angry, they call each other names or hit each other.⁴⁹ At the same time, such behavior ought not be a real issue. The proper adult response is laughter. Adults laugh, not just out of amusement at the ineffectiveness of the childish behavior, but also as a way to reprove and correct the child, since laughter undermines the original intent of the

⁴⁷ The pear theft is crucial in the work of Emiel Eyben, who tried to prove the existence of a youthful subculture in Roman Antiquity. See Eyben (1977) 179–80. The general index has an entry “groeps Moraal” on p. 672. From this, it appears that all passages denouncing the influence of peers are in fact from Christian authors; see also Eyben (1993).

⁴⁸ *Life of Theodore of Sykeon* 11, edited by Festugière (1970). I quote from the translation by Kalogeras (2001) 8–9.

⁴⁹ Ioh. Chrys. *Hom. epist. ad Hebraeos* 1.3 (PG 63, 17); *De inan. glor.* 31 (SC 188.124). See Leyerle (1997) 258.

child's behavior.⁵⁰ Only a fool would react to his child bearing tales such as, "Father, such and such hit me," by replying, "Such and such a one is a bad person. Let us hate him!"⁵¹

All together, the statement by the Church Father indicates a very different approach to childhood, which in no way focuses on psychological wellbeing the way we do in contemporary society.

4. Girls and Young Women under Constant Scrutiny

So far, nearly all of our examples have been young males. However, ancient historians have time and again pointed to Greco-Roman girls being under "pressure" of constant scrutiny and facing the danger of harassment. How to be a respectable virgin surely was a burden in ancient society, at least for the middle class and the well-to-do.⁵² But might teenage girls also be the victim of harassment by their male peers?

Women in Greco-Roman society married at an early age: by their late teens most were married to husbands who were in average in their mid-twenties.⁵³ Both the Greek and the Roman system insisted on the defining role of (in most cases) the father, by respectively the *kyreia* and the *patria potestas*. Over the centuries, there was an increasing emphasis on physical virginity, which is also apparent in the legal texts. Behaving modestly was the message for a young and marriageable girl. But what if she became the victim of rape or sexual assault by a young man? Was she still marriageable after this? Would she be viewed as "damaged goods?" The laws do not really deal with such problems, which elite families mostly attempted to solve by marrying off their daughters at even earlier age. Constant scrutiny was no doubt important. We should be aware of the many gaps in our evidence, and of situations never told or described. In the fictional controversies, rhetorical exercises which undoubtedly contained references to some kind of reality, we often find a reassertion of traditional values associated with girlhood.

⁵⁰ Ioh. Chrys. *Hom. 1 Kor.* 4.6 (PG 61.38); *Hom. epist. ad Hebraeos* 2.4 (PG 63.160); *Hom. Math.* 23.9 (PG 57.319). See Leyerle (1997) 258.

⁵¹ Ioh. Chrys. *Hom. epist. ad Col.* 4.4 (PG 62.330); *Adv. oppugnat.* 3.3 (PG 47.353–4). See Leyerle (1997) 258–9.

⁵² Recent literature, with reference to a plethora of previous scholarship includes Caldwell (2015) and Moraw, Kieburg (2014). An excellent comparison regarding supervision of young women before and during marriage in the Greek and Roman world in Bonnard, Dasen and Wilgaux (2017) 245–89.

⁵³ See the authoritative overview by Scheidel (2007).

Often in these controversies, girls choose marriage to the rapist, not his death. Glimpses of understanding are hard to find in these declamations.⁵⁴

Even marriage at a very early age could not always secure a girl against the accusation of illicit sexual activity. In fact, Roman law accepted that a girl who was taken as a bride before age twelve (the legal minimum) could still be accused of adultery, defined as sexual activity outside of marriage.⁵⁵

The Elder Seneca's *Controversia* 2.7 is a fictitious case of a young married woman, presumably in her teens or early twenties (since she appears to be childless), who had been harassed by a young and unmarried merchant (*adulescens* would put him between the age of fifteen and thirty). At stake is a regulation stating that a woman was considered adulterous if she accepted money from the adulterer.⁵⁶ The author adds that she would be adulterous according to the Lex Iulia, which implied that her crime was punishable by death (Sen. *Controv.* 2.7 *pr.* and 2):⁵⁷

A man with a beautiful wife went off abroad. A foreign trader moved into the woman's neighborhood. He three times made her propositions of a sexual nature, offering sums of money (*ter illam appellavit de stupro adiectis pretiis*). She said no. The trader died, leaving her all his wealth in his will, to which he added the clause: "I found her chaste." She took the bequest. The husband returned and accuses her of adultery on suspicion.

I know what instructions I gave my wife on my departure; you must apply to rumour for the rest (*interrogate rumore*), for the story of how a handsome, rich and unknown young man (*adulescens*) moved into the neighborhood of a beautiful woman, one who was all too free in the absence of her husband, how by continually satisfying his lusts night and day he exhausted his strength and died. (trans. M. Winterbottom)

⁵⁴ Sen. *Controv.* 3.5: *curo vulnera*—a father speaking; Quint. *Decl. Min.* 368: *solent dolere raptae*. See the excellent account by Caldwell (2015) 50–66.

⁵⁵ *Dig.* 48.5.14.8 (stating that the male adulterer could not be accused of adultery, since the girl was before marriageable age) and *Dig.* 47.10.15.24. See Caldwell (2015) 120–3.

⁵⁶ Hoebenreich (2015) is a rich article which carefully analyzes the Controversy.

⁵⁷ *Dig.* 48.5.34.2: *Si uxor ex adulterio viri praemium acceperit, lege Iulia quasi adultera tenetur*. Punishable by death: *Dig.* 48.6.5.2 (*ultimo supplicio*).

From the prologue, we learn that the accusation was about suspicion of adultery. This was more difficult to prove than an action *in flagranti*.⁵⁸ The arguments used by the “accusing party” shine a light on the difficulties harassed girls might face “There is no reason for her to say: ‘I couldn’t help it’ ... A married woman must go out dressed up only so far as to avoid unkemptness (*immunda*). Let her have companions old enough, at the very least, to make the shameless respect their years” (2.7.3). “If you go out with face made up to look utterly seductive, with almost naked dress, with conversation full of jest, acting so that no-one who sees you is afraid of approaching you: then be surprised” (2.7.4). “You think you’ll prove your chastity quite sufficiently if you merely say no to sex” (2.7.5). “Why did you not veil the beauty which could give the beholder such pleasure? Asked for sex, she keeps silent—the next thing to promising it” (2.7.6). “For a woman, in fact, the one glory is chastity; so she must take care to be chaste—and to be seen as chaste” (2.7.9). On the contrary, the defense of the *pars altera* is remarkably short and succinct: “She is beautiful: that was nature’s fault. She was alone: that was her husband’s fault. She was tempted: that was the fault of another. She said no: that was done chastely. She was left money: that was a stroke of fortune. She took the bequest: that was only prudent” (2.7 *pars altera*; trans. M. Winterbottom).

This Senecan Controversy needs to be understood in the context of Roman legislation which even included laws against “stalking” or “harassment.” *Appellare* refers to inappropriate compliments (tempting, allusive speech, convincing speech⁵⁹), whereas *adsectari* to the act of following a lady so closely and frequently that it nearly becomes harassment, insinuating an inexistent intimacy.⁶⁰

It is well known that the early church created almost a monopoly on virginity. To Christian authors, marriage was outshone by virginity and widowhood.⁶¹ Suffice it to notice here that John Chrysostom again points to problems parents might have with their daughters. Apparently, fathers had the imminent danger of harassment in mind. Although girls were usually considered more docile, if they turned unruly, they posed their own problems.⁶² If a daughter refused to stay inside as she got older, a careful father would lay down strict rules that she not show

⁵⁸ Hoebenreich (2015) 279.

⁵⁹ See also *Dig.* 47.10.15.15 (the way the young girls’ dresses are taken into account); and 47.10.15.23 (distinguishing between playfully addressing a person, or to go against sound morals). See Hoebenreich (2015) 287.

⁶⁰ *Dig.* 47.10.15.20-22 (trans. A. Watson). See Laes (2017) 70–1 on Roman girls and their chaste bodies.

⁶¹ From the vast literature, I only cite Harper (2013).

⁶² Ioh. Chrys. *De inan. glor.* 90 (*SC* 188.196); *Hom. 1 Timoth.* 9.2 (*PG* 62.547–8). See Leyerle (1997) 256.

herself outside the house or appear to passers-by; if she disobeyed, she might find her feet tied.⁶³

5. Adolescents and University Life

Student life in so-called “universities” of the ancient world has attracted scholarly attention. Indeed, at these ancient “universities” we see young males, roughly between age sixteen and twenty, who spent time away from their parental homes and indulged in activities which were only allowed by society because they were students.⁶⁴ For antiquity, this is perhaps the closest one comes to a sort of youthful subculture. One indeed finds complaints and sorrows on students’ behavior in sources as wide ranging as Cicero’s letters, papyri, Libanius and extended passages with both Latin and Greek Church Fathers from the fourth and fifth century, even up to late ancient sources of the sixth century.⁶⁵

But would the students’ lifestyle also include bullying between peers? We do have some so-called ego-documents, in which students themselves speak up. We know that the twenty-year-old Marcus Cicero wrote a letter to his father in which he repentantly confessed the mistakes of his party-filled student years, while at the same time indicating that he was doing better. From the papyri of the first or second century CE, we know of Nilus who wrote from Alexandria to his father Theon. He there complains about the misbehavior of his accompanying slave Heraclas. There are no traces, though, of bullying between peers in these ego-documents.⁶⁶

We again have to wait till late antiquity to find testimonies about bullying or threatening behavior among agemates. Even there, such passages are rare in comparison with the rich evidence on riots, brawls and rowdy behavior towards teachers. There is the testimony by Libanius, who reports about his arrival in Athens where he found himself in the hands of agemates—people he wanted none of. He was unable to even catch a glimpse of the teacher from whom he had come to learn and was cooped up in a cell about as big as a barrel. Though he had started crying for the teacher for whom he had come, his captors took no account of such outcries. Only after he had sworn an oath to put up with his present condition, was

⁶³ Ioh. Chrys. *Hom. in Genes.* 39.4 (PG53.366). See Leyerle (1997) 256.

⁶⁴ August. *Conf.* 5.8.14: “With extraordinary stupidity they commit their manifold outrages, which would be punishable by law but for the protection of custom” (trans. C. J-B. Hammond).

⁶⁵ Laes and Strubbe (2014) 92–9, also giving an overview of scholarship on the matter. See the vivid accounts in Cribiore (2001) and (2007); Watts (2006).

⁶⁶ See Cic. *Att.* 14.7.2 and 14.13.4; *Fam.* 16.21 (the letter by Marcus Cicero). For Nilus, see *P. Oxy* 18.2190.

the door opened and was he allowed to attend the lectures of Diophantus and two other sophists.⁶⁷

When he was studying with the rhetor in Carthage, Augustine took pride in not being fully part of the gangs of so-called *eversores*. Their “devilish” behavior consisted of brutally harassing and mocking newcomers (*ignotorum* most probably referred to newly arrived students). From the eloquent passage, it is clear that nasty humor and deriding others was part and parcel of the *eversores’* strategy (August. *Conf.* 3.3.6):

I was top of the class in the rhetor’s schoolroom. I revelled in my arrogance, I was puffed up with pride, although, Lord, as you know, I was much more restrained than the Destroyers who were always causing destruction (their name is sinister, devilish, but still a badge of sophistication), and firmly distanced from them. I lived among them, but with a kind of brazen embarrassment, for I was not one of them. I spent time with them and occasionally enjoyed friendships with them, but I used to shudder at what they got up to, namely the havoc that in their insolence they used to inflict upon the modesty of newcomers. They would attack them without provocation, jeering and then gratifying their malevolent pleasures (*hoc est ab eversionibus quibus proterve insectabantur ignotorum verecundiam, quam proturbarent gratis inludendo atque inde pascendo malivolas laetitiās suas*). There is no behavior more akin to demonic activity than this. So “Destroyers” is the perfect name for them. Certainly they are themselves destroyed and corrupted first, when the spirits of darkness and deceit mock and seduce them by that very behavior with which they love to mock and deceive others (*eversi plane prius ipsi atque perversi, deridentibus eos et seducentibus fallacibus occulte spiritibus in eo ipso quod alios inridere amant et fallere*).
(trans. C. J-B. Hammond)

Student baptism, which consisted of a cortege to and a ceremony in the bathhouse,⁶⁸ could also lead to bullying behavior. According to Eunapius, mockery and derision were very common.⁶⁹ Some authors recall the ceremony with a certain degree of nostalgia and fondness, stating that things did not get out

⁶⁷ See Eun. *VS* 495: Libanius fell in the trap of students of Diophantus: ἐνεδρευθεῖς δὲ ὑπὸ τῶν Διοφαντείων, Διοφάντῳ προσένειμεν ἑαυτὸν· καί, ὡς οἱ πάνυ τὸν ἄνδρα καταμεμαθηκότες ἔφασκον.

⁶⁸ Full descriptions in Greg. Naz. *Or.* 43.16; Olymp. *Hist. apud Photium*, p. 60 B; Zacharias, *Vita Severi*, p. 47 (ed. Kugener).

⁶⁹ Eun. *VS* 10, 1: ἡ τότε νεότης ἐς αὐτοὺς ἐπεδείκνυτο καὶ χλευασίαν καὶ γέλωτα.

of hand.⁷⁰ Gregory of Nazianze plainly states that the ceremony merely looks fierce to those who were not acquainted with it. According to him, there was never any real threat, only the creation of a threatening atmosphere.⁷¹ Yet it is obvious that reality was not always as nice. Eunapius himself was spared the ceremony, as he was not in good health at that time, and his sophist Prohaeresius had asked to treat him mildly during the ceremony.⁷² But more importantly, we have the following testimony from a fourth-century imperial edict, in which the allusion to violence and bullying behavior towards newcomers is obvious (*Constitutio "Omnem" de conceptione digestarum* 9):

In order that nobody ... would neither dare to do games which are unworthy and bad, moreover degrading and with an unjust effect, nor other crimes both against the teachers themselves and against their fellow students, and more importantly against those who come to the teaching of laws without any former knowledge. How could someone call these games, out of which crimes begin? We will in no way tolerate this.⁷³

6. Conclusions

6.1 Reality and Everyday Life

In an important recent article, Reider Aasgaard has set out some criteria to find out whether texts bring us closer towards ancient childhood and youth.⁷⁴ The anecdotes I have discussed here surely meet some of these criteria. We came across attestations by adults that ascribe certain behavior as typical of children and youth. In rare cases, adult writers distance themselves explicitly from bullying behavior or recognize it as characteristic of children. In some anecdotes, we see glimpses of children's everyday world: role play games in which the dominant role of one party can be used to nasty effects, violent play in the streets, schools as a place of tensions and rivalry, gangs of young people with elements of group

⁷⁰ Lib. *Ep.* 1458.

⁷¹ Greg. Naz. *Or.* 43.16: Καὶ τὸ πρᾶγμα, τοῖς μὲν ἀγνοοῦσι λίαν φοβερόν καὶ ἀνήμερον, τοῖς δὲ προειδόσι καὶ μάλα ἡδὺ καὶ φιλόανθρωπον· πλείων γὰρ ἔστιν ἢ ἐνδείξις ἢ τὸ ἔργον τῶν ἀπειλουμένων.

⁷² Eun. *VS*10.1.

⁷³ *Nemo audeat... indignos et pessimos, immo magis serviles et quorum effectus iniuria est ludos exercere et alia crimina vel in ipsos professores vel in socios suos et maxime in eos, qui rudes ad recitationem legum perveniunt, perpetrare. Quis enim ludos appellet eos, ex quibus crimina oriuntur? Hoc enim nullo patimur modo.*

⁷⁴ Aasgaard (2017).

pressure, unpleasant and persistent mocking of physical blemishes, student life in the tumultuous university towns. For girls and young women the context was different, but surely not less pressing, as they were subjected to constant social scrutiny within the setting of an honor-based society. In addition to the need to keep up appearances for society at large, they could also become the victim of insistent young men. As such, a survey of instances of bullying and harassment can be illuminating for those who want to gain insight into children and everyday life in Antiquity. At the same time, it is striking how seldom ancient writers chose to narrate experiences in which children and young people appear as “bullying or harassing agents.”⁷⁵ The theme is seldom explored, and there is hardly any reflection on how adults should respond to bullying behavior, which was regarded as rather trivial, and surely not worthy of extended pedagogical or psychological concern.

6.2 Not an Important Theme

Surely the Greek and Latin biographers rarely explored with concrete examples the enormous potential of bullying for the plot of one’s life. There is a specific reason for this, which brings us to the core of ancient concepts of personality and individuality. In an ongoing discussion on nature versus nurture, the ancient writers explicitly sided with nature. Their view of personality is essentially a static one: character and personality were considered to be present from early childhood. Education was therefore often described as a matter of disciplining and shaping into fully-fledged adults. Development was seen as a rise from a state of imperfection to a disciplined and controlled aristocratic way of life.⁷⁶

This view clashes with our way of thinking, which stresses how bullying can be a traumatizing experience. Does bullying really do children any harm? “Of course it does. It gets you, slowly but surely, before you turn into someone like me, full of hatred and longing for revenge”⁷⁷—one could also have added “full of low self-esteem and grief.” Such views are very much at the heart of our concerns towards school bullying: we believe that such experience will drastically shape and influence the personality of the children involved. This would not have been the view of ancient biographers. There are many examples to illustrate this. The emperor Caligula in his childhood years was living in the court of the tyrannical

⁷⁵ Eyben (1977) 627–81 has roughly 4,200 references in the Index Locorum. The subject index has at best fifteen references under the heading “plagerij” (which means “teasing” rather than “bullying”).

⁷⁶ Pelling (1990); Most (2008). See also Laes (2011) 96–9.

⁷⁷ Rigby (2002) 18.

Tiberius on the island of Capri. His two brothers had since been declared enemies of the state and killed by the emperor. He managed to survive by allowing all the insults to roll over him with masterful indifference. Moreover, he had put the calamities committed against his family so thoroughly out of his mind that it seemed as if they had never occurred.⁷⁸ Was he a traumatized young adult? Not so, according to Suetonius. Caligula's cruel and sadistic nature was already revealed in his young years.⁷⁹ Other emperors had also been accused of having been cruel from childhood years on.⁸⁰ For such views, a passage in the Life of emperor Commodus is crucial, in which the author even displays some irony towards teachers too confident of themselves (SHA *Comm.* 1.7):

However, teachers in all these studies profited him not in the least—such is the power, either of natural character, or of the tutors maintained in a palace. For even from his earliest years he was base and dishonorable, and cruel and lewd, defiled of mouth. (trans. D. Magie)

Even when one would almost instinctively expect a counterexample to such thinking, ancient biographers continue on the path of natural disposition. Such was the case with Plutarch, for whom the bullying of Cato Minor by a visitor, threatening to throw the child out of the window, or the sexual harassment of a young boy during an apparently innocent game only served as a confirmation of Cato's austere and enduring character, not as an explanation for it (cf. pp. 39–40 above). Also, in Plutarch, we read about the republican hero Coriolanus, whose merits towards Rome were somehow ambivalent (Plut. *Cor.* 1.2–4):

He showed, however, that such loss of a father, although otherwise bad for a boy, need not prevent him from becoming a worthy and excellent man, and that it is wrong for worthless men to lay upon it the blame for their perverted natures, which are due, as they say, to early neglect. On the other hand, the same Marcius bore witness for those who hold that a generous and noble nature, if it lack discipline, is apt to produce much that is worthless along with its better fruits,

⁷⁸ Suet. *Calig.* 10. On the death of Caligula's brothers, see Suet. *Tib.* 54.

⁷⁹ Suet. *Tib.* 57 (by his teacher of rhetoric Theodorus of Gada); also, by emperor Tiberius himself who realized that he was raising a snake for the Roman people (Suet. *Calig.* 10–11).

⁸⁰ SHA *M. Ant.* 5.3: *natura truculentus* ("fierce by nature"); SHA *Diadum.* 8.3: *istum ultra aetatem saevisse* ("he was cruel beyond his years").

like a rich soil deprived of the husbandman's culture. For while the force and vigor of his intelligence, which knew no limitations, led him into great undertakings, and such as were productive of the highest results, still, on the other hand, since he indulged a vehement temper and displayed an unswerving pertinacity, it made him a difficult and unsuitable associate for others. ... Verily, among all the benefits which men derive from the favor of the Muses, none other is so great as that softening of the nature which is produced by culture and discipline, the nature being induced by culture to take on moderation and cast off excess. (trans. B. Perrin)

Even the case of emperor Caracalla, who was said to have been a nice boy in his first childhood years, in no way serves as a counterexample.⁸¹ The examples of his "good behavior" merely serve to show how a "decent and good child" ought to behave. Indeed, there was no specific traumatizing bullying context that had "spoiled" the nice child (SHA *M. Ant.* 2.1):

All this, however, was in his boyhood. For when he passed beyond the age of a boy, either by his father's advice or through a natural cunning (*calliditate ingenii*), or because he thought that he must imitate Alexander of Macedonia, he became more reserved and stern and even somewhat savage in expression, and indeed so much so that many were unable to believe that he was the same person whom they had known as a boy. (trans. D. Magie)

⁸¹ SHA *M. Ant.* 1.3–8: "He himself in his boyhood was winsome and clever, respectful to his parents and courteous to his parents' friends, beloved by the people, popular with the senate, and well able to further his own interests in winning affection. Never did he seem backward in letters or slow in deeds of kindness, never niggardly in largess or tardy in forgiving—at least while under his parents. For example, if ever he saw condemned criminals pitted against wild beasts, he wept or turned away his eyes, and this was more than pleasing to the people. Once, when a child of seven, hearing that a certain playmate of his had been severely scourged for adopting the religion of the Jews, he long refused to look at either the boy's father or his own, because he regarded them as responsible for the scourging. It was at his plea, moreover, that their ancient rights were restored to the citizens of Antioch and Byzantium, with whom Severus had become angry because they had given aid to Niger. He conceived a hatred for Plautianus because of his cruelty. And all the gifts he received from his father on the occasion of the Sigillaria he presented of his own accord to his dependents or to his teachers" (trans. D. Magie) For another good childhood in an emperor's life (Gordianus Iunior), see SHA *Gord. tres* 18.1: "always in childhood, when one the boys (*puerorum*) was flogged, he wept" (trans. D. Magie).

6.3 Christianity and Change?

At first glance, it seems as if the Christian material, especially the many remarks we find in the writings of John Chrysostom or the Byzantine hagiographers, are richer in evidence as regards bullying. Of course, one is perfectly entitled to “enjoy” this rich information and vignettes of daily life scenarios as they are served up to the audience. However, the Christian writers do not even come close to a psychologizing approach of bullying or harassment, let alone a conceptualizing or problematizing of it. When we do find interest in human psychology with them, it is in fact within the context of psychology as a moral science, a typical late antique view.⁸² To John Chrysostom, children are like adults untutored in virtuous restraint. They are in need of socialization—and this process endorses his major concerns with the moral formation of his congregation. In hagiographical stories, the saints are mostly there as set and stable characters from early childhood on. Their being set apart from schoolmates, or their enduring of bad behavior by peers, are proof of sainthood already perceptible in the early years. In more introspective scenarios, in which authors reflect on their own youthful sins and their conversion, we see Saint Augustine being conscious of bullying behavior and peer pressure. But again, such behavior merely serves as a counterexample to the virtuous life of the convert afterwards—it is never presented as a psychological trigger with lasting influence on later life.

In a world which was full of violence and all sorts of behavior that are threatening to the development of young people, bullying children and children being bullied by peers were hardly a matter of concern. In all, life was hard in both the city and the country. Disasters were an in-built part of ordinary life in the Greco-Roman world that put large numbers of people in situations of extreme stress.⁸³ In such environment, bullying and harassment were only a minor cause for concern. At the same time, ancient writers show an awareness of and a care for the young ones in society, who were generally valued and cherished. Their depictions of bullying behavior are more on the level of moralizing anecdotes, but now and then they strike us as close to home and somehow similar. As such, these stories stem from a world and context which are profoundly different from ours—different, but at the same time recognizable.

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⁸² Leyerle (1997) 181.

⁸³ Toner (2009) and (2013).

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